

Breeding methods

Death of thermosensitive genic male sterile seedlings in Malaysian ricefields

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One hundred and fifty-four thermo-sensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) lines were introduced in Malaysia from the National Agricultural Research Center in Japan. The lines were bred from indica and japonica crosses and comprised 31 family lines, ranging from B₁F₉ to F₄. These TGMS lines were transplanted in ricefields at MARDI during the 1994-95 dry season (Nov-Feb) and the 1995 wet season (Apr-Aug). Some of the plants in 18 family lines died during the dry season (see figure).

Seedlings died in four of the five lines of the H91-4 family line, and no sterile plants were found (see table). In

Dead seedlings in Malaysian ricefield, 3 wk after transplanting.

the next generation of TG-3, which originated from the fertile plants of the TG-3 line, plants were segregated into fertile and sterile. This trait came from PL12, which contains a single and recessive TGMS gene. The segregation ratio of the TGMS plants, however, was less than the expected ratio (1/4). Three out of five lines of the H92-62 family line also had seedling deaths. TG-22, TG-23, TG-24, and TG-25 had some sterile plants. In the next generation of TG-23, plants were segregated into

fertile and sterile. The same phenomenon was observed in the H93-106 family line. Thirteen out of 18 family lines showed the same phenomenon. All five lines of the H92-150 family line showed more seedling deaths than the lines previously mentioned. TG-43 and TG-44 had a few sterile plants. All plants were fertile in the next generation of TG-43 and TG-44. Two out of 18 family lines showed the same phenomenon.

This type of seedling death rate has not been observed in nonTGMS lines introduced from Japan, and the phenomenon has never occurred in Japan. The 30-yr average temperature during the seedling growth month for Tokyo is 18.4 °C and that for Kuala Lumpur is 25.9 °C.

Seedling death was observed only during high temperatures. Germination of TGMS seeds was also poor. We suspect that the high temperature caused the TGMS seedlings to die.

The phenomenon observed in H91-4 can be explained as follows: all the TGMS seedlings died from high temperature, so no TGMS plants lived to flower in the hot dry season. But the TGMS gene in heterozygous plants was expressed and both fertile and sterile plants were produced in the next generation. The phenomenon of H92-62 was different from that of H91-4. Perhaps only a few of the TGMS seedlings died from high temperature. For H92-150, we believe most of the TGMS seedlings and the fertile plants, including the TGMS heterozygous plants, died from the high temperature.

The conclusions drawn from this study are speculative and need further confirmation through studies conducted with controlled temperature. Family lines with dead seedlings, however, cannot be used to produce hybrid seed. Further selection has to be done to eliminate this trait. Thirteen out of 31 family lines did not show this phenomenon and can therefore be used as parents for hybrids. ■

Dead seedlings in four TGMS family lines. MARDI, Penang, Malaysia. 1994-95.

Line	Family line	Combination	Generation	Dead/total seedlings	Sterile plants (no.)	Next generation
TG-1	H91-4	H89-1//H89-1/ Mangetsumochi	B ₁ F ₉	1/20	0	Fertile; sterile segregation
TG-2				0/20	0	
TG-3				3/20	0	
TG-4				1/20	0	
TG-5				2/20	0	
TG-21	H92-62	H89-1/X88	F ₁₀	0/20	0	Fertile; sterile segregation
TG-22				6/20	2/14	
TG-23				3/10	2/7	
TG-24				12/20	2/8	
TG-25				4/20	6/16	
TG-41	H92-150	H89-1/Mansoek//H87-35	F ₉	4/20	0	All fertile plants
TG-42				8/20	0	
TG-43				11/20	1/9	
TG-44				10/20	1/10	
TG-45				4/20	0	
TG-56	H93-106	PL12/90SL495	F ₇	7/20	3/13	Fertile, sterile segregation
TG-57				5/20	3/15	
TG-58				2/20	0	
TG-59				5/20	0	
TG-60				2/20	1/18	